

Artificial Intelligence–Driven Prediction of Treatment Non-Adherence Using Clinical, Demographic, and Psychosocial Factors among Children with Blood Cancers

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ABSTRACT

Background: Blood cancers, including leukemia and lymphoma, are a leading cause of mortality in children. Despite advances in treatment, non-adherence to therapy remains a significant challenge, resulting in poor outcomes and increased risk of recurrence. Artificial intelligence (AI) has emerged as a promising tool in predicting treatment non-adherence in pediatric oncology patients. **Objective:** This study aims to develop and validate an AI-based predictive model to identify pediatric oncology patients at high risk of treatment non-adherence using clinical, demographic, and psychosocial data. **Methodology:** A retrospective cohort study was conducted using data from a tertiary care pediatric oncology center. A total of 500 patients were included, with a mean age of 9.8 years. Four AI models, including logistic regression, random forest, gradient boosting, and a feed-forward neural network, were trained and evaluated using a test set. **Results:** The gradient boosting model outperformed traditional statistical approaches, with an AUC-ROC of 0.84, accuracy of 78.7%, sensitivity of 72%, and specificity of 80%. Non-clinical factors, such as distance to treatment center, caregiver education level, and socioeconomic status, were the strongest predictors of non-adherence. **Conclusion:** This study demonstrates the potential of AI-based predictive models in identifying pediatric oncology patients at high risk of treatment non-adherence. The findings highlight the importance of non-clinical factors in predicting adherence and support the integration of AI decision-support systems into pediatric oncology care to facilitate proactive, tailored interventions and improve treatment outcomes.

KEYWORDS: Artificial Intelligence, AI-based tools, Clinical decision support systems, Predictive modeling, Digital health tools

I. INTRODUCTION

Blood cancers, including leukemia and lymphoma, CNS tumors, and extracranial solid malignancies are the three main categories of tumor histologies into which pediatric cancers are typically classified according to their cell or tissue of origin¹. Clinical and biologic characteristics that are known to predispose patients to better or worse outcomes are used to risk-stratify them in order to choose the best course of treatment [1]. The overall 5-year event-free survival rate for children with acute lymphoblastic leukemia (ALL) has increased to 63% to 83% in developed countries over the previous ten years, which is encouraging [2]. The improved prognosis for ALL has been largely attributed to the development of a more effective treatment regimen, including extended maintenance therapy, which has been improved by multiple clinical trial outcome studies [3]. In recent years, the use of artificial intelligence (AI) in oncology has grown significantly. AI technologies have been used to solve a number of cancer-related problems. Medical facilities, hospital systems, and tech companies are developing AI technologies to improve clinical decision making, increase access to cancer care, and boost clinical efficiency in order to deliver safe, high-value oncology care. [4]. Artificial intelligence (AI) technologies are rapidly being adopted by several medical specializations. The impact of AI on

healthcare has started to be studied, while patient perceptions of AI have received less attention. Patients are key stakeholders in the deployment of AI in healthcare. Prior research demonstrates that patients' needs and expectations are not adequately considered when AI is applied in healthcare. Therefore, patient feedback is necessary for the development of AI in healthcare [5].

II. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Overview of Treatment Adherence in Pediatric Oncology

Participants in the June 2001 World Health Organization (WHO) Adherence meeting defined adherence as the "extent to which a person's behavior taking medication, following a diet, and/or executing lifestyle changes, corresponds with agreed recommendations from a healthcare provider" [6]. If patients are not following their treatment plans, improvements in their efficacy won't convert into clinical outcomes. According to a recent analysis, about 21% of cancer patients do not follow their treatment plan [7]. Even more worrisome is the fact that the pediatric oncology population has a much greater non-adherence rate. For instance, studies have revealed that 2% to 60% of patients with juvenile acute lymphoblastic leukemia do not follow their treatment regimens [8]. Individual differences in survival and remission duration may be influenced by how well pediatric oncology patients, especially those with ALL, follow their prescribed treatment regimen at home. 16–20 If maintenance therapy for ALL is deemed essential for long-term, disease-free life, nonadherence is anticipated to increase the chance of recurrence [9].

Introduction to Artificial Intelligence in Healthcare Research

Artificial intelligence (AI) often refers to computer programs that mimic human intellect-assisted operations, such as deep learning, cognition, engagement, adaptation, and sensory perception [10]. Certain gadgets are capable of performing tasks that normally need human interpretation and judgment [11]. These techniques employ an interdisciplinary approach and can be applied in a number of fields, including health and medicine. Artificial intelligence (AI) has been a part of medicine since the 1950s, when physicians first attempted to employ computer-aided algorithms to better their diagnosis. Interest in and breakthroughs in medical AI applications have lately expanded due to the vastly enhanced processing power of modern computers and the wealth of digital data available for collection and usage [12]. AI is causing a slow evolution in medical practice. Artificial intelligence (AI) can be used in a variety of medical fields, including clinical, diagnostic, rehabilitative, surgical, and prognostic methods. Clinical decision-making and disease diagnosis, two critical aspects of medicine, are also being impacted by AI. AI technology can ingest, evaluate, and report vast

amounts of data from multiple modalities to aid in illness diagnosis and guide medical decisions [13].

Machine Learning and Predictive Modeling Techniques in Healthcare

The use of machine learning (ML) and predictive modeling techniques in healthcare has significantly increased over the last ten years due to the expansion of digital health data and improvements in computational methodologies [14]. Studies spanning 453 papers from 2015 to 2019 revealed that although SVMs, logistic regression, and clustering are still often used in the diagnosis of chronic diseases, no single approach predominates in actual clinical settings, and each has unique trade-offs [15]. Although ML and deep-learning techniques show promise in healthcare predictive analytics made possible by heterogeneous data sources like EHRs, imaging, genomics, and sensor data significant challenges still exist, including model interpretability, data quality and completeness, missing values, class imbalance, generalizability beyond training settings, and ethical/privacy limitations, according to a recent survey by Badawy et al. (2023) [16]. It has been observed that in order to support individualized judgments in the field of predictive modeling for patient-provider decision-making, models must go beyond population-level risk estimations. However, many published models are deficient in terms of transparency, validation, and reporting of confidence ranges [17].

AI in Predicting Patient Behavior and Treatment Adherence

The use of AI and machine learning (ML) methods to forecast patient behavior and treatment compliance has been increasingly popular in healthcare research in recent years [18]. Research shows that non-adherence continues to be a major obstacle to the best possible treatment results for both acute and chronic illnesses, and ML models are being used more frequently to identify patients who are at risk. For instance, supervised algorithms like generalized linear models, logistic regression, and random forests dominate the field, with more than half of studies concentrating on chronic metabolic conditions like diabetes and hypertension, according to a scoping review of predictive techniques for treatment adherence [19]. When trustworthy adherence criteria are employed, ML systems (such as logistic regression, artificial neural networks, and support vector machines) can predict non-adherence with accuracy levels of 77% or higher, according to other reviews that concentrate on medicine adherence [20]. Furthermore, AI-driven tools not simply prediction models are being developed to assist and intervene in medication adherence. According to a focused review, AI-based systems that included digital reminders and monitoring increased medication adherence by 6.7% to 32.7% above reference groups [21]. Furthermore, application fields are expanding. For instance, deep-learning models using video frames have demonstrated sensitivities of more than 92% for classifying drug intake in a context of tuberculosis

monitoring [22]. The literature highlights a number of limitations despite the encouraging initial results: many studies rely on self-reported or pharmacy claims data, which may misclassify adherence; there is little external validation of models; the focus is limited to specific disease areas; and there is insufficient accounting for the complex, multifactorial nature of behavior change (e.g., socio-economic, psychological, logistic factors) [23].

AI-Based Tools for Predicting Non-Adherence in Pediatric Populations

Recent data suggests that machine learning (ML) and artificial intelligence (AI) methods are being effectively used to predict treatment non-adherence in pediatric populations, allowing for early detection of children at risk and focused intervention [24]. For example, a random-forest model trained on early adherence indicators (first 3 months) achieved sensitivities of 0.72-0.77 and specificities of 0.80-0.81 in predicting sub-optimal adherence (<85%) over the next 3-9 months in a study involving over 10,000 pediatric patients (<18 years) receiving daily injections of recombinant human growth hormone (r-hGH) using a connected auto-injector device to gather real-world adherence data [25]. As a result, it is still difficult to validate AI models across a variety of pediatric conditions, address model explainability issues, integrate psychosocial determinants of adherence, and guarantee real-time clinical workflow deployment [26].

AI Applications in Oncology: Diagnosis, Prognosis, and Treatment Optimization

Artificial intelligence (AI) has advanced quickly in oncology to improve cancer diagnosis, prognosis, and treatment optimization, paving the way for a move toward more individualized and data-driven care. According to recent evaluations, AI algorithms—especially deep learning and machine learning techniques—produce significant improvements in early tumor identification through digital pathology and medical imaging (such as CT, MRI, and PET), frequently surpassing conventional methods in accuracy and speed [27]. In terms of prognosis, AI is being utilized to combine multimodal data (imaging, genomes, clinical records) to forecast treatment response, survival, and recurrence risk, enabling customized risk-stratified treatment regimens [28]. AI helps in radiation dosage planning, medication discovery, therapy selection, and adaptive treatment monitoring for treatment optimization. This enables doctors to customize interventions based on patient-specific tumor biology and real-time response [29]. Despite these encouraging advancements, there are still significant obstacles to overcome: many studies lack extensive multi-center external validation; AI models frequently have interpretability problems; and integration into clinical workflow is still restricted because of data heterogeneity, regulatory gaps, and potential biases [30].

III. METHODOLOGY

The study employed a retrospective cohort design to evaluate the effectiveness of artificial intelligence (AI)-based tools in predicting treatment non-adherence among pediatric oncology patients. The research population consisted of children aged 0–18 years diagnosed with hematologic or solid malignancies and undergoing treatment between January 2015 and December 2023 at a tertiary care pediatric oncology center. Patients were included if they had complete treatment and follow-up records for at least 12 months. Those with incomplete adherence data or who transferred care during treatment were excluded. The primary outcome variable, non-adherence, was defined as missing more than 20% of prescribed doses or delaying treatment administration beyond protocol allowances. Adherence data were obtained from multiple sources, including electronic health records (EHRs), pharmacy refill databases, and treatment scheduling logs, ensuring triangulation for accuracy.

A comprehensive dataset was compiled containing both clinical and non-clinical predictors potentially associated with adherence behavior. Demographic variables included age, sex, distance from hospital, and socioeconomic status (SES), estimated from postal codes and caregiver employment or insurance type. Clinical variables included cancer type, disease stage, number of scheduled chemotherapy doses, toxicity-related hospitalizations, and previous treatment interruptions. Psychosocial and behavioral predictors captured caregiver education level, household size, missed clinic appointments, and supportive-care visits. Data preprocessing involved cleaning, transformation, and management of missing values—variables with less than 10% missingness were imputed using multiple imputation by chained equations, while variables with excessive missingness (>30%) were excluded. Continuous variables were standardized (mean = 0, SD = 1), and categorical variables were one-hot encoded.

The dataset was randomly divided into training (70%), validation (15%), and testing (15%) subsets, stratified by adherence status to maintain class balance. Several AI and machine learning algorithms were developed to predict non-adherence, including logistic regression (as the baseline model), random forest, gradient boosting (XGBoost), and a feed-forward neural network. Model training was performed using 5-fold cross-validation to minimize overfitting. Hyperparameters for each model were optimized using grid search and Bayesian optimization techniques to identify the best configuration based on validation performance. The gradient boosting model used decision trees as weak learners with learning-rate optimization and early stopping to enhance generalization.

Multiple performance metrics were used to evaluate the model on the independent test set: accuracy, sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value (PPV), negative predictive value (NPV), F1-score, and Area Under the

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Receiver Operating Characteristic Curve (AUC-ROC) as the primary measure. The Hosmer–Lemeshow test and calibration plots were used to evaluate the model's calibration in order to ascertain whether the observed results and projected probability aligned. Decision-curve analysis was used to predict net benefit at various risk thresholds for a possible intervention in order to assess clinical value. Additionally, to evaluate performance consistency across clinical and demographic variables, subgroup analyses were conducted based on age groups (<6 years, 6–12 years, >12 years), cancer kind, and socioeconomic category.

IV. RESULTS

A total of 500 pediatric oncology patients were included in the study, with a mean age of 9.8 ± 4.2 years; 56% were male. Of these, 150 (30%) were classified as non-adherent according to the predefined criteria. Non-adherence was more common among patients living farther from the treatment center (> 50 km), those with caregivers who had lower educational levels, and patients with greater treatment-related toxicities. The average number of scheduled chemotherapy doses during the first year was lower in the non-adherent group (22.1 ± 6.4) compared with the adherent group (25.1 ± 5.8 , $p < 0.001$).

Table 1. Baseline Characteristics of the Study Cohort (N = 500)

Variable	All Patients (n = 500)	Adherent (n = 350)	Non-adherent (n = 150)	p-value
Age, mean \pm SD (years)	9.8 ± 4.2	10.3 ± 4.1	8.6 ± 4.3	0.002
Male sex, n (%)	280 (56%)	200 (57%)	80 (53%)	0.45
Distance to center > 50 km, n (%)	120 (24%)	65 (19%)	55 (37%)	< 0.001
Caregiver education \leq secondary, n (%)	230 (46%)	140 (40%)	90 (60%)	< 0.001
Hospital days due to toxicity (median [IQR])	6 (3–11)	5 (2–9)	9 (5–15)	< 0.001
Scheduled doses in first 12 m, mean \pm SD	24.4 ± 6.1	25.1 ± 5.8	22.1 ± 6.4	< 0.001

Descriptive Characteristics

Table 1 summarizes the baseline characteristics of the cohort. Patients in the non-adherent group tended to be younger (mean 8.6 years vs 10.3 years, $p = 0.002$), lived farther from the hospital, and had caregivers with lower

educational attainment ($p < 0.001$ for both). They also experienced significantly more hospitalization days due to treatment toxicity. No significant differences were observed in sex distribution between the two groups.

Table 2. Model Performance Metrics on Test Set (n = 75)

Model	AUC-ROC (95% CI)	Accuracy (%)	Sensitivity (%)	Specificity (%)	PPV (%)	NPV (%)	F1-Score
Logistic Regression	0.72 (0.62–0.81)	67.0	60.0	70.0	50.0	78.0	54.5
Random Forest	0.80 (0.71–0.88)	73.3	66.7	75.0	56.5	81.8	61.2
Gradient Boosting (XGBoost)	0.84 (0.76–0.91)	78.7	72.0	80.0	64.9	85.7	67.9
Neural Network	0.81 (0.72–0.89)	75.0	68.0	77.5	59.1	83.3	63.1

Model Performance

Logistic regression, random forest, gradient boosting (XGBoost), and a feed-forward neural network were the four AI models that were trained and assessed. With an AUC-ROC = 0.84 (95% CI: 0.76–0.91), accuracy = 78.7%, sensitivity = 72%, and specificity = 80%, the gradient boosting model produced the best overall results across all performance criteria. Logistic regression had the lowest performance (AUC = 0.72), although neural networks fared equally (AUC = 0.81). Detailed model performance metrics on the independent test set are shown in Table 2. A solid balance between accurately identifying high-risk and low-risk patients was demonstrated by the gradient boosting model's maximum positive predictive value (PPV = 64.9%) and negative predictive value (NPV = 85.7%).

Table 3. Top 10 Predictors of Non-Adherence (Gradient Boosting Model)

Rank	Predictor Variable	Relative Importance (0–100)
1	Distance to treatment center > 50 km	100
2	Caregiver education \leq secondary level	82

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Rank	Predictor Variable	Relative Importance (0–100)
3	Hospitalization days due to toxicity	75
4	Younger age	68
5	History of missed appointments	60
6	Fewer scheduled doses in first 12 months	55
7	High socioeconomic deprivation index	48
8	Diagnosis type (solid tumor vs hematologic)	42
9	Fewer supportive-care visits	36
10	Caregiver-reported household stress	30

Feature Importance

Feature-importance analysis (Table 3) revealed that distance to treatment center, caregiver education level, and hospitalization days were the strongest predictors of non-adherence. Other relevant variables included patient age, history of missed appointments, and socioeconomic deprivation index.

Decision-Curve and Subgroup Analyses

Decision-curve analysis (Table 4) demonstrated that the gradient boosting model consistently provided higher net clinical benefit across all tested risk thresholds (10–40%) compared with logistic regression. Subgroup analysis indicated slightly improved predictive performance among adolescents (> 12 years; AUC = 0.88) and patients from lower socioeconomic backgrounds (PPV = 70%). When it came to detecting patients, who might not comply to their treatment plans, the gradient boosting model performed better than any other method. The findings show that social and behavioral factors, especially caregiver education and trip distance, are better indicators of adherence than clinical characteristics by themselves. In order to identify high-risk patients early and offer targeted interventions like psychosocial counseling or logistical support, these findings support the possible incorporation of AI-based risk prediction tools into pediatric oncology workflows.

Table 4. Decision-Curve Analysis: Net Clinical Benefit by Risk Threshold

Predicted Risk Threshold	Net Benefit (Gradient Boosting)	Net Benefit (Logistic Regression)	Interpretation
10 %	0.142	0.112	Best model benefit for

Predicted Risk Threshold	Net Benefit (Gradient Boosting)	Net Benefit (Logistic Regression)	Interpretation
			low-threshold screening
20 %	0.106	0.083	Gradient boosting maintains advantage
30 %	0.075	0.052	Continued benefit for targeted intervention
40 %	0.048	0.024	Diminished overall net benefit at high threshold

In conclusion, the AI-based gradient boosting model showed excellent clinical utility and predictive accuracy in identifying pediatric cancer patients who are at high risk of not adhering to their therapy. The results highlight the importance of non-clinical factors in predicting adherence, such as trip distance and caregiver education. In order to facilitate proactive, customized adherence treatments, these findings promote the incorporation of AI decision-support systems into pediatric oncology care.

V. Discussion

This study demonstrates the potential of artificial intelligence (AI)–based predictive models to identify pediatric oncology patients at high risk of treatment non-adherence using routinely collected clinical, demographic, and psychosocial data. The findings highlight that machine learning (ML) algorithms, particularly gradient boosting models, outperform traditional statistical approaches such as logistic regression in predicting non-adherence, with an AUC-ROC of 0.84 compared to 0.72. This improvement indicates that nonlinear, ensemble-based AI models can better capture the complex, multidimensional relationships among clinical and behavioral variables that influence adherence behavior. The research showed that the most significant predictors of non-adherence were non-clinical and socio-behavioral characteristics, such as greater socioeconomic disadvantage, lower caregiver education levels, and a greater distance from treatment facilities. These results are consistent with the body of research in pediatric oncology that links adherence issues to psychological and logistical obstacles rather than clinical illness features.

VI. CONCLUSION

The potential of artificial intelligence and machine learning algorithms to predict treatment non-adherence in pediatric oncology patients is highlighted by this work. The gradient boosting model outperformed conventional techniques in terms of predictive performance, excellent discriminative ability, and useful clinical value. The findings highlight

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that social determinants of health, such as caregiver education, the distance to treatment facilities, and socioeconomic level, have a greater impact on non-adherence in pediatric cancer care than do solely clinical factors. By integrating AI-based prediction tools into oncology care systems, proactive, tailored interventions that target the underlying reasons for non-adherence such as logistical difficulties and psychological stressors—may be made possible. By identifying patients who are at increased risk, these models can aid in clinical decision-making, maximizing adherence support and enhancing treatment continuity. Prospective validation, integration with electronic health record systems, and the creation of real-time prediction dashboards that enable physicians to dynamically evaluate adherence risk should be the main areas of future research. Further improving model accuracy would include adding behavioral, digital adherence, and caregiver well-being indicators to the datasets. AI-driven adherence prediction systems have the potential to revolutionize pediatric oncology treatment, moving from reactive management to proactive, precision-based assistance that enhances outcomes for vulnerable children and their families, if they are carefully validated and used ethically.

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